

Anaphylactic Reaction Induced by Multivitamin Infusion: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Anaphylaxis is a serious, life-threatening hypersensitivity reaction triggered by the rapid release of mediators from mast cells and basophils. It commonly results in symptoms such as urticaria, vasodilation, oedema, and bronchoconstriction. Drugs, particularly antibiotics, NSAIDs, and injected radiocontrast agents, are frequent culprits of anaphylaxis in adults. This article describes the case of a 44-year-old male diagnosed with anemia and is experiencing an anaphylactic reaction to an intravenous multivitamin infusion. The patient, who had no prior medical history or drug allergies, presented with generalized fatigue and headaches. Complete blood count and endoscopy were performed. During hospitalization, the patient was managed with various medications, including multivitamins, antacids, and iron supplements. However, shortly after the administration of the multivitamin infusion, the patient developed signs of anaphylaxis. The adverse reaction was promptly treated with medications. Causality assessment using the WHO Naranjo scale was assessed for this reaction. This case highlights the potential for life-threatening anaphylaxis in response to commonly used medications and emphasizes the importance of monitoring for adverse reactions during drug administration.

Keywords: Anaphylaxis, Microcytic hypochromic anemia, drug-induced reactions, multivitamin infusion, adverse drug reactions.

Introduction:

Anaphylaxis is a serious, potentially life-threatening systemic allergic reaction that results from the swift release of mediators from mast cells and basophils through the process of

degranulation ^[1]. This condition is marked by the discharge of vasoactive substances, including histamine, tryptase, and prostaglandin-leukotriene mediators. Histamine is released rapidly and can be detected in peripheral blood within 5 to 10 minutes after the reaction starts. Serum levels of tryptase peak between 60–90 minutes after the onset of anaphylaxis and may stay elevated for as long as 24 hours. Both markers are beneficial for tracking the anaphylactic response. IgE-mediated reactions arise from antigenic stimulation, which intensifies the immune response and can be assessed. Specifically, the IgE response displays a Th2 pattern, distinguished by heightened levels of IL-4 and IL-13 along with diminished levels of IFN- γ and IL-12. Furthermore, the role of TNF- α in anaphylactic reactions has also been documented ^[2]. Medications are the primary triggers of anaphylaxis among adults. The most frequently implicated drugs include antibiotics (mostly penicillin and cephalosporins), nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory agents, injected radiocontrast substances (such as iodinated contrast media and gadolinium), cancer treatment drugs, therapeutic antibodies, and neuromuscular-blocking agents (NMBAs) that are utilized during surgeries. These mediators often lead to urticaria, vasodilation, increased vascular permeability, fluid leakage, edema, and bronchoconstriction, culminating in reduced arterial pressure, tachycardia, bronchospasm, and gastrointestinal disturbances. Anemia refers to a decrease in red blood cells and reflects an underlying condition rather than serving as a diagnosis. Symptoms vary based on the cause, the speed of onset, and other health conditions, particularly cardiovascular issues. Erythropoietin (EPO), which is produced by the kidneys, stimulates the production of red blood cells in response to tissue hypoxia. EPO levels increase with low hemoglobin but are often insufficient in cases of renal failure or anemia of chronic disease (AOCd). Normal hemoglobin ranges are as follows: Men: 13.5–18.0 g/dL; Women: 12.0–15.0 g/dL; Children: 11.0–16.0 g/dL; Pregnancy: >10.0 g/dL, depending on the trimester.

Iron, an essential element of hemoglobin, acts as the main carrier of oxygen. A decline in the body's iron reserves hinders hemoglobin production, which disrupts oxygen delivery to the body's organs. Anemia reduces the blood's capacity to transport oxygen, resulting in tissue hypoxia. It is usually diagnosed through hematocrit (the percentage of packed red blood cells in blood volume) and hemoglobin levels. Microcytic anemia occurs due to impaired hemoglobin (Hb) production in erythroid precursors, leading to a reduced mean corpuscular volume (MCV) in red blood cells (RBCs). Microcytic, hypochromic anemia is a type of anemia where red blood cells are smaller than normal (microcytic) and look paler because of reduced hemoglobin levels (hypochromic) [3].

Types of Anemia

- 1.Hypoproliferative microcytic anemia
- 2.Hypoproliferative Normocytic anemia
- 3.Hypoproliferative Macrocytic anemia

2. Case Description:

A 44-year-old male was admitted to the general medicine male ward with the chief complaints of generalized tiredness and headache on and off for 3 months. He had no past medical and medication history. He had no known drug allergies. The patient had a history of tobacco chewing. He was diagnosed with Anemia. On the day of admission, he was conscious, oriented, and afebrile. His vitals were as follows: Blood pressure: 130/70 mm Hg, heart rate: 80 beats per minute, respiratory rate: 19 breaths per minute, and body temperature: 97.2 are normal. His laboratory investigation shows decreased RBC, Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, and MCHC (Table 1). His peripheral smear study shows Microcytic hypochromic anemia. His endoscopy report shows

acute gastritis. Two units of PRBC was done. He had been managed with medications such as Vitamin supplements, Iron supplements, antacids and anti-depressants.

3. Discussion

In this case, the patient's prescribed medications are multivitamin Infusion 1500 mcg was given in 100 ml NS to treat nutritional deficiency; Inj. Pantoprazole (40 mg; 1-0-1) was given to treat acidity; T. Amitriptyline (10 mg; 0-0-1) was given to treat chronic headache; and T. Ferrous Fumarate & Folic Acid (5 mg; 0-1-0) was given to treat iron deficiency anemia. Inj. Ferric carboxymaltose 1 g was given to treat anemia. Multivitamin infusion composed of Retinol (Vit A) 1000 IU+ Thiamine (Vit B1) 5 mg + Niacinamide (Vit B3) 10 mg + D- Panthenol (Vit B5) 2,5 mg + Pyridoxine (Vit B6) 1.5 mg + Ascorbic acid (Vit C) 50 mg + Cholecalciferol (Vit D3) 100 IU +Tocopherol (Vit E) 50 mg was given to treat nutritional deficiency. Multivitamins infusion have serious rare adverse effects. Here, the patient experienced an anaphylactic reaction within 15 minutes of MVT infusion. He experienced cough, shortness of breath, sweating, palpitations, nausea, and dizziness. The adverse effects of the patient were managed by Inj. Chlorpheniramine 2 ml and Neb. Ipratropium bromide + Levosalbutamol (500 mcg + 1.25 mg) which was given to the patient. The WHO Naranjo's causality assessment scale scored 7, indicating probable adverse reactions in terms of severity (Table 2). As vitamins are necessary for the body to maintain its normal resistance, they can also result in anaphylactic reactions. Thiamine, often known as vitamin B1, is thought to be the most allergenic vitamin. An intravenous injection is associated with urticaria and anaphylaxis, but rapid (type I) reactions are uncommon ^[4]. **Tween-80** is a commonly used solvent to dissolve lipid-soluble medications such as vitamins A, C, D3, B1, B2, B6, E, and K. A rising number of research studies suggest that Tween-80 can induce anaphylactic reactions ^[5]. Tween 80 is non-immunologic and non-IgE-

mediated reactions. They directly activate the mast cells, and the complement system in the body leads to the release of histamine and other mediators. Histamine binds to the H1 receptor leads to increased vascular permeability, which leads to vasodilation; smooth muscle contraction results in shortness of breath and tachycardia. The complement system consists of a series of small proteins. It involves an anaphylactic reaction through the activation of C3a, C4a, and C5a. Of these, C3a and C5a can induce the release of histamine from the basophil and mast cells, which helps to exacerbate the anaphylactic reaction ^[6].

4. Conclusion

In this case report, we presented a rare instance of multivitamin-induced anaphylaxis, emphasizing the importance of recognizing this potentially life-threatening reaction. The clinical presentation, including rapid-onset symptoms and diagnostic findings, highlighted the need for prompt identification and management to prevent severe outcomes. Our case outcome underscores the critical role of managing anaphylaxis and optimizing patient safety. This report stresses the need for heightened awareness among clinicians regarding the potential allergenic components of multivitamin preparations and the importance of timely intervention to mitigate long-term complications and improve patient outcomes. Desensitization is an option for patients with vitamin hypersensitivity who need oral or intravenous supplementation and have no other therapeutic option.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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Tables:**Table 1: Laboratory Investigations**

Parameters	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5
RBC Million/Cmm	3.69	4.05	4.1	4.3	5.3
Hb (g/dl)	5.0	5.3	6.2	7.3	9.8
PCV (%)	18.6	20.9	31.2	24.8	30.7
MCV (cu. Microns)	50.5	51.7	76.1	56.6	61.1
sMCH (pg)	13.7	11.0	22.3	13.1	14.6
MCHC (g/dl)	27.2	21.3	29.3	23.1	23.9

Table 2: Naranjo's Scale

Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale				
Questions	Yes	No	Don't Know	Score of our case
1. Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	+1	0	0	+1
2. Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was administered?	+2	-1	0	+2
3. Did the adverse reaction improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was administered?	+1	0	0	+1
4. Did the adverse event reappear when the drug was re-administered?	+2	-1	0	-1
5. Are there alternative causes (other than the drug) that could on their own have caused the reaction?	-1	+2	0	+2
6. Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	-1	+1	0	+1
7. Was the drug detected in blood (or other fluids) in concentrations known to be toxic?	+1	0	0	0
8. Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	+1	0	0	0
9. Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	+1	0	0	0
10. Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	+1	0	0	+1